

Deliverable Document 4

The synergies with the NeIC NT1 operations *Overview of different deployments of EISCAT_3D e-infrastructure services*

E3DDS Team *

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*Anders Tjulin (EISCAT) anders.tjulin@eiscat.se; Ari Lukkarinen (CSC) ari.lukkarinen@csc.fi; Carl-Fredrik Enell (EISCAT) carl-fredrik.enell@eiscat.se; Dan Johan Jonsson (UiT) dan.jonsson@uit.no; Harri Hellgren (EISCAT) harri.hellgren@eiscat.se; Ingemar Häggström (EISCAT) ingemar.haggstrom@eiscat.se; Mattias Wadenstein (UmU) maswan@hpc2n.umu.se; John White (NeIC) john.white@cern.ch

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1 Executive Summary

This document describes the possible scenarios of deploying the EISCAT_3D e-infrastructure services with NeIC NT1 and other partners. The document details the services for EISCAT_3D operations and those suitable or not to be run by NeIC NT1 or other partners. The most beneficial deployment scenario is identified according to the factors considered in this document: Risks; Benefits; Cost Efficiency; Reliability; User Satisfaction. Steps to remedy the negative aspects of the most beneficial scenario are presented including the Service Level Agreements (SLAs) needed, service management (e.g. FitSM) required and the division of responsibilities. Estimates of the staffing effort required to run the EISCAT_3D services are presented as well as the effort to run NeIC NT1.

2 Purpose

This document shall function as a guideline for both EISCAT, their partners and NeIC in order to understand how the EISCAT_3D e-infrastructure services can be deployed. This document does not intend to draw hard conclusions on the deployment model, but gives an objective opinion on a series of factors to consider in each deployment scenario.

2.1 Intended Audience

The intended audience of this document is EISCAT_3D project management and EISCAT partners. in order to understand the deployment options for the EISCAT_3D e-infrastructure services. This document can be most efficiently deployed to the EISCAT_3D project management in its PDF form.

3 Introduction

The EISCAT Scientific Association will establish EISCAT_3D, a flexible multistatic high power radar system, that will enable comprehensive three-dimensional vector observations of the atmosphere and ionosphere above Northern Fenno-Scandinavia.

The use of new radar technology, combined with the latest advances within digital signal processing, will achieve ten times higher temporal and spatial resolution than obtained by the present EISCAT radar systems. For the first time, EISCAT will also be able to measure continuously. The flexibility of the EISCAT_3D system will enable scientists to investigate upper-atmospheric and ionospheric phenomena at both large and small scales unobtainable by the present systems.

In its first stage, the EISCAT_3D system will consist of three radar sites: one having both Transmitting and Receiving capabilities and two with only Receiving capability. The sites will be remote-controlled and located in three different countries (Finland, Norway and Sweden) and will be separated geographically by approximately 130 km. Two additional receiver sites, at distances 200-250 km from the transmit site, are planned for the full EISCAT_3D system at a later stage.

The EISCAT_3D radar is planned to be operated at near full-time ¹ (24/7) up-time and able to serve processed data to users in near real-time. In order for this to be achieved a set of computing, storage and network services ² must be put in place. Some of these e-infrastructure services operate in real-time i.e. must process data when the radar is running and the antennas are receiving signals. Other e-infrastructure services can be considered as more in the background and do not have to be run in real-time e.g. data management services serving high-level processed data to EISCAT_3D users.

4 EISCAT_3D e-infrastructure Services

The services shown in Table 1 are those estimated, at the time of writing, to be necessary for EISCAT_3D to: acquire data; process online and offline; produce data products in order to steer the radar; serve data to users for analysis.

The radar data is used to control subsequent radar transmission and receiver look directions. Therefore the online computing services must run in real-time while the radar is transmitting.

A service that is noted as “run by” (or “operated by”) EISCAT is a service that required specialized in-house knowledge that is unlikely to be found elsewhere. The “owned by” designation for a service refers to the management and ownership of the data in the service. For example, the “Site data buffer” disk array could be run by a non-EISCAT entity whereas the choices on the data to retain or remove from the disks are made by EISCAT. Another example is the “User portal web GUP” where typically operating a complex web portal is better left to experienced experts and the EISCAT users would access as clients where data retention etc is handled by central portal policies.

The priority of a service is defined by:

- **1 High:** Without this service the radar system CANNOT be run;
- **2 Medium:** The radar can still run but users cannot obtain data from the system;
- **3 Low:** Radar can run and data extracted but analysis and publishing not possible.

The following scenarios for running the EISCAT_3D e-infrastructure are considered. In these scenarios, the standard assumptions are:

- That the EISCAT_3D data is replicated to two redundant data archives.
- The EISCAT_3D radars are planned to run 24/7 ³

In each scenario the following factors are considered. The **Risks** and **Benefits** overall in having the various organizations running the services. The **Cost Efficiency** refers to how much effort an

¹The definition of the up-time of the EISCAT_3D radar is still to be determined.

²Generally described as e-infrastructure.

³this is a big caveat...

Service	Location	Real-time	Run by	Owned by	Priority	Comments
Radar controller	Skibotn or DC	Yes	EISCAT	EISCAT	1 High	Radar controller system
Ring buffer + Beam former + File Writer + Fast Imaging	Skibotn or all sites	Yes	EISCAT	EISCAT	1 High	RAM and fast disks
Prompt computing	TBD Skibotn or DC	Yes	EISCAT	EISCAT	1 High	Lag profiling (Level 1 to 2), parameter fitting (Level 2 to 3), visualisation (Level 3 on geographic coordinates)
Secondary data products	Co-located with prompt computing	No	Other	EISCAT	2 Medium	Standard data products that don't need to be produced in realtime e.g. full imaging
Identity management	One master site. Other secondary sites.	No	Other	EISCAT	2 Medium	Directory services for user identity management
Site data buffer	Co-located with prompt computing	Yes	Other	EISCAT	1 High	Fast disk storage for processing of data, levels 1b, 2, 3. Partition of long-term storage?
Cluster management etc	Sites	No	Other	EISCAT	1 High	Configuration and software deployment on RBBF, Prompt computing, admin login nodes etc.
User portal web GUI	TBD	No	Other	Other	2 Medium	User data discovery and job submission portal. DIRAC prototype exists.
User job management	TBD	No	Other	Other	2 Medium	Submit analysis jobs. DIRAC considered.
Data staging	Initially Skibotn storage	No	Other	Other	2 Medium	Prototype uses DIRAC storage element and file transfer
User compute	Initially using Prompt computing	No	Other	EISCAT	2 Medium	Computing resources for user analysis portal.
User software deployment	Complements User analysis portal	No	Other	Other	2 Medium	e.g. the DIRAC input sandbox
Interactive user software deployment	Complements User analysis portal	No	Other	Other	3 Low	e.g. Notebooks Jupyter or other?
Data archive	Data Centres	No	Other	EISCAT	2 Medium	Long-term data storage. Does EISCAT want to run a data archive?
Internal metadata catalog	Data Centres	Yes	Other	EISCAT	1 High	Metadata master catalogue e.g. metadata from Level 1b files. Realtime.
User metadata catalog	Data Centres	No	Other	EISCAT	2 Medium	Metadata for users. e.g. from higher level data products.
Data product repository	Close to long-term storage	No	Other	EISCAT	2 Medium	
Data product publishing	Close to long-term storage	No	Other	EISCAT	3 Low	e.g. FAIR compliant Repository for published datasets. E.g. B2SHARE.
Monitoring	Sites	Yes	Other	EISCAT	1 High	Environment and operational status. Possibly NAV software from Uninett.
Inventory	Skibotn	No	EISCAT	EISCAT	1 High	List of all parts (preferably marked with QR codes) and updates to status.
Public IP routing	Sites	Yes	NORDUnet	NORDUnet	3 Low	Internet access for technical staff and guest instruments.

Table 1: The e-infrastructure services required for EISCAT_3D.

organization will have to expend to run a set of service(s). **Reliability** describes whether the service up-time can be maintained in order to process and serve the data from the expected duty cycle of the radar operations. In these scenarios the “users” are the consumers of the EISCAT_3D data and the comments on **User Satisfaction** evaluates how this would be affected by each scenario.

The NeIC NT1 is one of 14 regional computing centres of the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid: the international e-infrastructure built to provide computing and storage for the Large Hadron Collider at CERN. This Nordic solution is unique in being distributed across four countries: Denmark, Finland, Norway and Sweden. NeIC NT1 is primarily an e-infrastructure operational programme that receives data as part of the World-Wide LHC Computing Grid [1] (WLCG). This data is archived and also served to scientific users for analysis. The data must be orchestrated over the many computing centres, disks and tapes all over Scandinavia.

4.1 Scenario 1

In this scenario EISCAT runs all the computing on-line and off-line services noted in Table 1 except for the second redundant external data archive i.e. the copy of the EISCAT_3D data.

Risks

- There is a risk for EISCAT Scientific Association not being able to recruit the required e-infrastructure staff with the correct skills into one organization.
- Retaining an excess of staff for full 24/7 coverage of EISCAT_3D services during vacations/illnesses/change of employment.
- New security certifications of staff to operate public-facing services. Includes GDPR etc.
- Incident impact higher with services/hardware in one place. Single point of failure.
- Running user-accessible computing close to the instrument is an IT security risk.

Benefits

- Hardware and staff are controlled through one set of EISCAT processes.
- No need to make special agreements with external parties for data confidentiality.

Cost Efficiency

- Usually it is not cost efficient for one organization to run all the services. Many varying services will require fractional amounts of effort.

- Cost efficiency will be impacted by the extra cost required to start and run complex services in production mode. Especially when considering this will replicate already existing services being run by other e-infrastructure projects e.g. EGI Check-in [2].
- Some services required (e.g. AAI or Web portals) for EISCAT_3D operations do not have synergies with the current EISCAT computing expertise.

Reliability

- Reliability improved as it is easier for operators to communicate within one organization.
- Reliability will be impacted in the startup phase for first years as operators will not be familiar with operating services in production mode.

User Satisfaction

- User satisfaction may be high as users are able to contact directly to EISCAT personnel for help with problems or questions.
- User satisfaction might be negatively impacted by a learning period for how to run many new services.

4.2 Scenario 2

The NeIC NT1 programme runs all computing services listed in Table 1 except the EISCAT_3D inventory system and the First Stage Receive Units [3] (FSRUs) under a service contract. In this scenario, the services are still physically located at the central site (nominally Skibotn) and a service contract is written with NeIC NT1 to run them. This scenario could also apply to a commercial computing provider e.g. IBM Global services.

Risks

- Recruiting lots of skilled IT staff into NeIC NT1 might fail. This can be seen as a lesser risk than in 4.1 as NeIC NT1 is by nature distributed over many institutes and countries.
- Some EISCAT_3D required services do not have synergies with current NeIC NT1.
- There would need to be complicated SLA negotiations to cover all services and data confidentiality i.e. something essential might not be covered by the agreement(s).
- As in 4.1, all services located physically at a central site gives a single point of failure.
- Running user-accessible computing close to the instrument is an IT security risk.

Benefits

- EISCAT would retain the control of the fundamental services most familiar for them i.e. operation of the FSRUs and the inventory databases.
- Hardware and staff for running all other services are controlled through a single set of NeIC NT1 processes.
- Recruiting into the NeIC NT1 will be easier as it is a distributed operation that can access a competence pool over the whole Nordic area. There are good synergies with home institutes of NeIC NT1 members.
- There is prior experience in writing service contracts for similar operations.
- EISCAT would be free to concentrate on running their critical services.

Cost Efficiency

- As with Scenario 1, it may not be cost efficient for one organization (NeIC NT1) to run all the services. Finding enough people with the necessary skills to run and maintain a wide variety of services is usually difficult.
- There is the risk of replicating existing services run by other e-infrastructure projects.
- Some of the required EISCAT_3D services does not have synergies with existing NeIC NT1 activities.

Reliability

- The reliability of some the services will be improved as the EISCAT_3D addition would be an increment on already existing NeIC NT1 services in production.
- Services that are not part of the NeIC NT1 core services would not necessarily be more reliable in this scenario i.e. might be impacted.
- Reliability improved as it is easier for the service operators to communicate within one organization.

User Satisfaction

- EISCAT_3D User satisfaction may be lowered as users will be required to more formally contact an external organization for help with problems or questions. Not contacting directly to other EISCAT colleagues.

Service	Location	Real-time	Run by	Owned by	Priority	Comments
Radar controller	Skibotn or DC	Yes	EISCAT	EISCAT	1 High	Radar controller system
Ring buffer + Beam former + File Writer + Fast Imaging	Skibotn or all sites	Yes	EISCAT	EISCAT	1 High	RAM and fast disks
Prompt computing	TBD Skibotn or DC	Yes	EISCAT	EISCAT	1 High	Lag profiling (Level 1 to 2), parameter fitting (Level 2 to 3), visualisation (Level 3 on geographic coordinates)
Site data buffer	Co-located with prompt computing	Yes	Other	EISCAT	1 High	Fast disk storage for processing of data, levels 1b, 2, 3. Partition of long-term storage?
Cluster management etc	Sites	No	Other	EISCAT	1 High	Configuration and software deployment on RBBF, Prompt computing, admin login nodes etc.
Internal metadata catalog	Data Centres	Yes	Other	EISCAT	1 High	Metadata master catalogue e.g. metadata from Level 1b files. Realtime.
Monitoring	Sites	Yes	Other	EISCAT	1 High	Environment and operational status. Possibly NAV software from Uninett.
Inventory	Skibotn	No	EISCAT	EISCAT	1 High	List of all parts (preferably marked with QR codes) and updates to status.

Table 2: The High-priority e-infrastructure services run by EISCAT (NeIC NT1) in Scenario 3 (5).

- User satisfaction might be negatively impacted by a learning period for how to run many new services. This is the same as in scenario 1.
- As NeIC NT1 may have an easier time recruiting staff and using existing skills at scientific computing centers in the Nordics, being able to draw on wider range of experience in running services should improve the user satisfaction.

4.3 Scenario 3

In this scenario EISCAT runs the high-priority services and outsources medium/low to their partners. Table 2 shows the services that EISCAT would run. The services listed in Table 2 can be seen to be more likely, and suitable, to be run at the Skibotn site. Table 3 gives the low and medium priority services run by partners and collaborators of EISCAT. These services, that can be run by EISCAT partners, are already part of their normal operations, for example: the DIRAC portal through EGI [4]. The services listed in Table 3 do not necessarily need to be physically located at the EISCAT_3D central site.

Risks

- Some services may be outsourced to unsuitable partners.

Service	Location	Real-time	Run by	Owned by	Priority	Comments
Secondary data products	Co-located with prompt computing	No	Other	EISCAT	2 Medium	Standard batch processing.
Identity management	One master site. Other secondary sites.	No	Other	EISCAT	2 Medium	e.g. EGI Checkin run by EGI partner?
User portal web GUI	TBD	No	Other	Other	2 Medium	DIRAC portal at RAL?
User job management	TBD	No	Other	Other	2 Medium	DIRAC portal at RAL?
Data staging	Initially Skibotn storage	No	Other	Other	2 Medium	NeIC NT1.
User compute	Initially using Prompt computing	No	Other	EISCAT	2 Medium	Academic Cloud provider. CSC?
User software deployment	Complements User analysis portal	No	Other	Other	2 Medium	DIRAC portal at EGI
Data archive	Data Centres	No	Other	EISCAT	2 Medium	NeIC NT1.
User metadata catalog	Data Centres	No	Other	EISCAT	2 Medium	NeIC NT1
Data product repository	Close to long-term storage	No	Other	EISCAT	2 Medium	NeIC NT1
User software deployment	Complements User analysis portal	No	Other	Other	3 Low	Partner University running Jupyter or other?
Data product publishing	Close to long-term storage	No	Other	EISCAT	3 Low	B2SHARE at CSC
Public IP routing	Sites	Yes	NORDUnet	NORDUnet	3 Low	NORDUnet.

Table 3: The Low and Medium-priority e-infrastructure services run by partners in Scenarios 3 and 5.

- SLAs may not be well-defined between multiple entities.
- If an EISCAT_3D service runs on a shared service, the future provision would be dependant upon the future funding of the other projects that use the service.
- Small risk that problems may be generated on services by other users.

Benefits

- EISCAT would retain the control of the high-priority services.
- EISCAT would not need to run unfamiliar services.
- For the “low” and “medium” services that are outsourced, most of them can probably be outsourced to suitable partners.
- A benefit in that the physical/administrative separation of services is good for overall IT security.

Cost Efficiency

- Cost efficiency improved if operators do not have to be re-trained if they are already familiar with the services.

- Cost efficiency improved if the partners can take in the EISCAT_3D load as a fractional increase on their existing workload.

Reliability

- Reliability improved as the services are run by operators already familiar with the services and the EISCAT_3D load is just a fractional increase on existing workload.
- Reliability improved as there will be more resources (hardware/support) for a larger redundant and resilient e-infrastructure installation running services for multiple communities.
- Reliability may be impacted as service operators will have to communicate between different organizations.

User Satisfaction

- May be impacted as users may have to formally contact service providers outside the EISCAT organization.
- Hopefully the service operators will be able to solve problems quickly due to experience.

4.4 Scenario 4

In scenario 4, EISCAT runs most of the services but outsources services with “obvious” synergies to other organizations. These organizations are either current EISCAT partners or new partners such as NeIC NT1 or other scientific computing centres in Europe. The criterion is that an organization already runs the service required by EISCAT_3D in their current normal operations. For example, the following organization run services required by EISCAT_3D and can be considered similarly to Section 4.3:

- The DIRAC User Portal [5] is already operated for other communities by GridPP [6] or EGI [4];
- Identity management services run by EGI for the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid [1] and others;
- Batch and academic Cloud computing at an academic computing centre that already operates large batch/cloud services;
- User software deployment (with someone that runs scientific computing)
- Data Archive, Data Staging, and Site Data Buffer could be synergistically run as one storage by NeIC NT1;
- Data product repository and publishing;
- Metadata and file catalogues operated by an institute that is already running Rucio [7]

Risks

- SLAs that are not well-defined.
- Small risk that problems may be generated on services by other users. This risk can be considered as even smaller than Section 4.3.

Benefits

- EISCAT would retain the control of the high-priority services.
- EISCAT would not need to run unfamiliar services.
- A benefit in that the physical/administrative separation of services is good for overall IT security.
- Services are run by organizations best suited and already operating such services.
- As organizations already operate the services in production mode, 24/7 coverage is more likely to be achieved.
- Being part of a large group of users will ease software transitions due new versions or the need to migrate to a completely different product.

Cost Efficiency

- Operators do not have to be re-trained as already familiar with the services.
- The organizations can take in the EISCAT_3D load as a fractional increase on their existing workload.

Reliability

- Reliability improved as the services are run by operators already familiar with the services and the EISCAT_3D load is just a fractional increase on existing workload.
- Reliability improved as there will be more resources (hardware/support) for a larger redundant and resilient e-infrastructure installation running services for multiple communities.
- Reliability may be impacted as service operators will have to communicate between different organizations.

User Satisfaction

- User satisfaction may be impacted as EISCAT users will still have to formally contact external organizations for problems/requests.
- The User Satisfaction should not be negatively impacted by service interruptions as the services are now run by organizations already suited to the task.

4.5 Scenario 5

Scenario 5 is similar to (Section 4.3) but in this case NeIC NT1 runs the high-priority services (as defined in Table 2) under a service contract and EISCAT outsources the medium and low priority services (Table 3) to partners. Therefore NeIC NT1 is running the online data production and the offline services are run by partners other than EISCAT. The assumption that EISCAT will operate the FSRUs and inventory system still holds.

Risks

- The operations setup of NeIC NT1 is probably not suitable for running online data production.
- SLAs for online data production between EISCAT Scientific Association and NeIC NT1 may be hard to achieve.
- Recruiting lots of skilled IT staff into NeIC NT1 for online operations might fail.
- Under-estimate by NeIC NT1 of amount of FTEs required to run online services.
- Other medium and low priority services may be outsourced to unsuitable partners.

Benefits

- EISCAT can concentrate on core scientific (non-computing) operations.

Cost Efficiency

- Cost efficiency for high priority services run by NeIC NT1 will probably not improve. These are not an incremental addition to an already-existing operation.
- Cost efficiency for medium and low priority services may be improved if operators do not have to be re-trained if they are already familiar with the services.
- Cost efficiency for medium and low priority services may be improved if the partners can take in the EISCAT_3D load as a fractional increase on their existing workload.

Reliability

- The reliability for medium and low priority services will not be impacted and may improve as these services are designated to be run by operators already familiar with the services i.e. they have an obvious synergy.
- The reliability for high priority services that are to be run by NeIC NT1 may suffer. NeIC NT1 is not an programme used to running online data production.
- Reliability may be impacted as service operators will have to communicate between different organizations.

User Satisfaction

- User satisfaction may suffer as EISCAT users will have to formally contact external organizations for problems/requests.
- Without a clear case for improved reliability user satisfaction will suffer.

4.6 Scenario 6

In scenario 6: NeIC NT1 operates the in-house services for EISCAT: those that do not have obvious synergy with the EISCAT partners, under a service contract. This scenario has similarities to Section 4.2 and Section 4.4 but in this case NeIC NT1 operates EISCAT's inhouse resources under a service contract. Examples of the EISCAT_3D service that have obvious synergies with partners are given in Section 4.4. The in-house EISCAT_3D services that would be run by NeIC NT1 would be the high priority online data production. The assumption that EISCAT will operate the FSRUs and inventory system still holds.

Risks

- The operations setup of NeIC NT1 is probably not suitable for running online data production.
- SLAs for online data production may be hard to achieve.
- Recruiting lots of skilled IT staff into NeIC NT1 for online operations might fail.
- Under-estimate by NeIC NT1 of amount of FTEs required to run online services.
- Other medium and low priority services may be outsourced to unsuitable partners.

Benefits

- EISCAT can concentrate on core scientific operations.

Cost Efficiency

- Cost efficiency for high priority services run by NeIC NT1 will probably not improve. These are not an incremental addition to an already-existing operation.
- Cost efficiency for medium and low priority services may be improved if operators do not have to be re-trained if they are already familiar with the services.
- Cost efficiency for medium and low priority services may be improved if the partners can take in the EISCAT_3D load as a fractional increase on their existing workload.

Reliability

- Reliability for medium and low priority services may be improved as the services are run by operators already familiar with the services.
- Reliability impacted negatively for high priority services run by NeIC NT1 as these services are not familiar.
- Reliability may be impacted as service operators will have to communicate between different organizations.

User Satisfaction

- User satisfaction may suffer as EISCAT users will have to formally contact external organizations for problems/requests.
- Without a clear case for improved reliability user satisfaction will suffer.

5 Summary

The scenarios in Sections 4.1 through 4.6 are summarized in Table 4 to see how the deployment of the EISCAT_3D operations. The summation of the factors is made with the following procedure:

- The positives (blue) and negatives (red) in each factor are counted.
- Factors that were positive or negative for high-priority services were given a double weighting.
- If the total number factors (positive or negative) is greater than 3 then a "strongly" rating is applied.

Table 4 gives a visual representation of the factors. All scenarios carry a certain amount of risk. All scenarios provide benefits with three (4.2, 4.3, 4.4) providing significant benefits. The two scenarios (4.1, 4.2), where one organization runs all services are not cost efficient whereas the

Factors	Scenario Section					
	4.1	4.2	4.3	4.4	4.5	4.6
Risks	X	X	X	X	X	X
Benefits	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Cost Efficiency	X	X	✓	✓	–	–
Reliability	–	✓	✓	✓	X	X
User Satisfaction	–	X	–	–	X	X

Table 4: Summary table of the factors considered for the EISCAT_3D services deployment scenario sections. (Dark) blue indicates (strongly) positive summation of factors for EISCAT_3D. (Dark) red indicates (strongly) negative summation of factors for EISCAT_3D.

scenarios where services are spread have better cost efficiency. The reliability of services are seen to suffer in the scenarios (4.5, 4.6), where high priority services could be run by unsuited hosting organizations. The expected user satisfaction is generally seen to vary little between the scenarios.

5.1 Most Beneficial Scenario

The deployment scenario with the most promising outcome in Table 4 is 4.4. The risks in 4.4 and other negative aspects can be mitigated.

The Service Level Agreements can be better defined if the following steps are taken:

- Careful selection in allowing only organizations to host EISCAT_3D services they already run as part of their operations.
- Well defined up-time and duty cycle of the EISCAT_3D radar operations.
- Well-defined expectation of the relation between the radar operation and the service operation.
- Use of existing SLAs between organizations for academic computing.
- Use of a standardized syntax e.g. FitSM [8] within SLAs.

The other risk is that problems may be generated by other users on services shared (operated) with EISCAT_3D. This risk is considered to be lower than in 4.3 where the low/medium services are out-sourced to partners without the requirement that the service is already run by the hosting organization. The risk that these problems arise can be reduced by:

- Understanding the delineations and separations within a service hosted by an organization for each client.
- Requiring critical parts of a service to be separated within a hosting organization.

It is noted in 4.4 that service reliability may be impacted as service operators will have to communicate between different organizations. A service may experience a break if it is dependent on another service that is not available (crash, updates, network problems etc) and run by another operator.

- In order to improve the communications between operators and EISCAT_3D, a common dashboard should be used between all operators.
- Similarly, a common problem ticketing system can be used between all operators.

In the factors for User satisfaction it is noted that there may be an impact as EISCAT_3D users will still have to formally contact external organizations for problems/requests. Given that some services are run by organizations other than EISCAT, this is unavoidable but the following action can be taken to mitigate this issue:

- Set up a single interface for EISCAT_3D users to submit problem reports or service requests.

5.2 NeIC NT1

The NeIC NT1 runs data services for the Nordic Data Grid Facility [9] (NDGF) Tier-1 centre for the World-wide LHC Computing Grid [1] (WLCG). NeIC NT1 stores ≈ 20 PB of data for the Alice and ATLAS communities serving several thousands of users. Average data read speed is 5 GB/s with peaks at over 10 Gb/s. The storage for the NDGF Tier-1 is distributed across many computing centres. The dCache [10] system, developed with contribution from NeIC, orchestrates the data stored on disks and tapes all over Scandinavia. It also accepts data transfers to and from CERN and other Tier-1 centres.

- 24/7 operator on call.
- On-call operator is able to log in to storage e-infrastructure on all sites in order to effect repairs and re-start services etc.
- Core services are repaired 24/7.
- Non-core services are repaired on the next working day.

The effort budgeted to run the NeIC NT1 programme, based on the requirements above, is given in Table 5.

5.3 Effort estimates

The effort required to run the e-infrastructure services for EISCAT_3D is given in Table 6.

Task	Target FTE
Operator on Duty	0.8
Management and reporting	0.3
dCache central ops and tarpools	0.7
dCache development, R&D and maintenance, incl ENDIT plugins	1
PostgreSQL database management	0.2
Monitoring including Nagios, 'ELK', Ganglia, Site BDII	0.5
Automatization and basic infrastructure services for headnodes	0.5
Site Security Officer role and security in general	0.2
Accounting and database management	0.25
Accounting system development and maintenance	0.25
WLCG project participation	1
ARC development	0.5
NeIC community services	0.1
SUM	6.3

Table 5: The effort budgeted to run the NeIC NT1.

Services	Low Estimate	High Estimate
Cluster management: linux admin, systems monitoring, and security for each administrative domain.	1 FTE. Very good synergies with teams that already have a fabric management setup)	2 FTE Standalone
Beamforming and prompt computing	0.5-1 FTE	
Databases: inventory, internal metadata catalog, and experiment control system	1-3 FTE	
Site data buffer	0.5 FTE Buying "ready in a box" high cost lustre/GPFS installation. Could also be included in data product repository for very low marginal cost	2 FTE For more flexible software on commodity hardware e.g. ceph/eos/dcache.
Site monitoring	0.5-1.5 FTE EISCAT	
Identity management	0.5 FTE Integration with external system	2-4 FTE Running own services
DIRAC portal	0.5 FTE Shared infrastructure including customization	2+ FTE Running own services
Data management, including data product repository, data staging and data archive	1 FTE As part of current NT1 system + Rucio at RAL	4+ FTE Dedicated systems with little synergy
User compute	0.5 FTE Shared at somewhere that already runs batch computing	1-2 FTE A dedicated resource
User software deployment and support	0.5-3 FTE Depending on level of support required	
User metadata catalog	Varies. e.g. using Rucio layer for collections and letting the metadata catalog have much fewer entries will ease operational burden	
Data product publishing	0.5-1 FTE	
Internal network operations including monitoring	0.5 FTE As part of NT1	1 FTE As standalone

Table 6: The estimated effort to run e-infrastructure services required for EISCAT_3D in Full Time Equivalents (FTE).

Table 6 gives the estimates to run these services on two assumptions: the “Low Estimate” in which services are run either in a shared mode or using a suitable partner as the service operator. The following services have a strong synergy with services currently operated by NeIC NT1 and can be considered as good candidates to be run by this programme:

- Data staging;
- Data archive;
- Site data buffer;
- User compute;
- Data archive copy;
- User metadata catalogue.

The following services have a medium synergy with services currently operated by NeIC NT1 and might be considered as candidates to be run by this programme with more investigation:

- Cluster management;
- Part of the databases (low level DB admin, not experiment control system).

5.4 SLAs and service management

Service Level Agreements [11] (SLAs) define boundaries between the organizations and who has responsibility for what parts. In the case for EISCAT_3D these SLAs need to focus on defining the common problems envisioned and encourage an atmosphere of cooperation for the overall good of science.

Service management should be carefully tuned based on the cost of failure for a particular service, but recognizing that a too formal framework will stifle creativity and efficiency. Building a bridge needs strong safety standards, while writing a book needs far less legislation.

Important failure modes and their costs should be identified by EISCAT, for instance:

- Loss of data taking due to beamformer etc failure;
- Loss of existing data due to storage failure;
- Leak of embargoed data, not intended for publication;
- End user needing to resubmit an analysis job due to a computer crash;
- Misleading metadata in catalog.
- ...

Over-estimate of cost of failure for services can lead to inefficient service management i.e. too many resources committed to prevent a failure, and a lack of agility to adopt to new circumstances. Under-estimate of the cost of failure can lead to too frequent costly (economical, loss of reputation, etc) failures.

Service management for data access to data should be well-defined and formalized in order to prevent leaks of embargoed data or data not intended for publication. Whereas the user compute e-infrastructure, which might require new libraries and programs to be available on a shorter time-scale can have a less rigid update policy.

Highly skilled staff can also help mitigate the need for highly formalized processes, in fact a highly formalized process might be detrimental to keeping highly skilled staff motivated and eager to work with the systems.

A good understanding of these aspects should lead to well-written SLAs where the provider can use appropriate service management approaches for various services. A good example of this in academic computing is the usage of FitSM [8].

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Appendix A Author Information

Name	email address	ORCID
Simon Brown	simon.brown@eiscat.se	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9879-5838
Carl-Fredrik Enell	carl-fredrik.enell@eiscat.se	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1006-2822
Ingemar Häggström	ingemar.haggstrom@eiscat.se	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1070-6915
Harri Hellgren	harri.hellgren@eiscat.se	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3351-2929
Dan Johan Jonsson	dan.jonsson@uit.no	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6698-6920
Ari Lukkarinen	ari.lukkarinen@csc.fi	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6662-8306
Anders Tjulin	anders.tjulin@eiscat.se	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3810-2937
Mattias Wadenstein	maswan@hpc2n.umu.se	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2682-2059
John White	john.white@cern.ch	https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5614-0895